

ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS FOR HYPERTENSIVE CRISIS

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Abstract. A hypertensive crisis is a sudden and significant increase in blood pressure to critical levels, which may be accompanied by target organ damage, such as the heart, brain, and kidneys. In such situations, the timely use of antihypertensive agents is vital.

Keywords: Hypertensive crisis. Antihypertensive agents. Urapidil.

The relevance of antihypertensive agents in hypertensive crises is determined by the following factors:

1. Rapid reduction of blood pressure: Antihypertensive drugs help to quickly reduce blood pressure to safe levels, reducing the risk of serious complications, such as stroke or myocardial infarction.

2. Prevention of target organ damage: Blood pressure control reduces the strain on vital organs, preventing damage and dysfunction.

3. Improvement of patient prognosis: Timely and adequate treatment of hypertensive crises using antihypertensive agents improves long-term outcomes and the patient's quality of life.

The main groups of antihypertensive agents used in hypertensive crises:

- Vasodilators (e.g., sodium nitroprusside): They dilate blood vessels, reducing total peripheral resistance.

- Beta-blockers (e.g., esmolol): They reduce heart rate and myocardial contractility.

- Diuretics (e.g., furosemide): They promote fluid excretion, reducing the volume of circulating blood.

- ACE inhibitors (e.g., enalaprilat): They prevent the formation of angiotensin II, reducing vasoconstriction.

Antihypertensive agents are a key component in the treatment of hypertensive crises. Their use allows for the rapid and effective reduction of blood pressure, preventing serious complications, and improving the course of the disease. Timely medical assistance and the correct choice of therapy are crucial for a favorable patient prognosis.

Objective: To evaluate the efficacy and safety of urapidil hydrochloride in the management of hypertensive crises complicated by hemorrhagic stroke.

Methods. The study included patients over the age of 18 with hypertensive crises complicated by hemorrhagic stroke. The patients were randomly assigned

by random number method to the urapidil hydrochloride treatment group ($n = 19$) and the control group receiving standard antihypertensive therapy in the hospital ($n = 14$).

Results. In the urapidil hydrochloride group, target blood pressure levels were achieved in all patients by the 20th minute after administration (from 207 (203–224) mm Hg to 151 (145–160) mm Hg (median, lower, and upper quartiles), $p < 0.0001$), whereas in the standard treatment group, blood pressure reduction took longer. In both groups, a statistically significant reduction in blood pressure was observed over the study period (220 minutes): $p < 0.0001$ in the urapidil hydrochloride group and $p = 0.00079$ in the control group (Friedman-Kendall statistics). At the start of the study, there were no differences in systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ($p = 0.1$). From the 20th minute onward, both SBP and DBP were statistically significantly lower in the urapidil hydrochloride group — SBP (151 (145–160) mm Hg at the 20th minute and 142 (138–146) mm Hg at the 220th minute; in the control group — 186 (170–206) mm Hg at the 20th minute and 168 (146–180) mm Hg at the 220th minute (p from 0.0001 to 0.07 by Mann-Whitney). Similarly, DBP behaved in both groups. There was little increase in heart rate (HR) in the urapidil hydrochloride group. In the control group, HR decreased by the 220th minute ($p = 0.002$), remaining within normal values in both groups. Patient survival was assessed at 1.5 months after the start of treatment. It was found that cumulative survival was significantly higher in the group of patients receiving urapidil hydrochloride (Log-rank $p = 0.01$; Gehan-Wilcoxon $p = 0.0015$). Cumulative survival was not dependent on age or sex. The volume of intracerebral hematoma greater or less than 34 ml had a weakly significant effect on survival.

Conclusions. Urapidil hydrochloride is an effective and safe drug for the treatment of patients with hypertensive crises complicated by hemorrhagic stroke.

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